

Perceived Attitude of Facebook Users Towards Memes About Depression

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ABSTRACT

The primary purpose of the study is to determine whether other people's attitudes and memes expressing depression influence how users perceive depressed people. The descriptive-correlational study approach was used to emphasize the degree of attitude toward depression and the frequency of interaction with memes that express depression among three hundred eighty-five random participants residing in Surigao del Norte. The statistical analysis tools that were used in treating the data were frequency count, mean, standard deviation, Pearson Correlation, and One-way ANOVA. Females between the ages of twenty and twenty-four comprise the majority of those who interact with memes that express depression and majority of the participants oftentimes interact with memes expressing depression. Results showed that there is a significant relationship between the participants' attitude towards depression and their frequency of interaction with memes that express depression. When it comes to memes expressing depression, individuals are more likely to take them seriously than humorously. Moreover, results also showed that there is a significant difference between perceived attitude towards depression when grouped by sex. Furthermore, the null hypothesis that states there is no significant difference between the participants' attitude towards depression and their frequency of interaction with memes that express depression when grouped according to their profile: Age, was rejected. As a result, it's critical to encourage Facebook users to exercise caution while interacting with memes that express depression.

Keywords: *Attitude, Facebook Users, Memes, Depression*

INTRODUCTION

According to Rogers (2021), memes are a spread of reproduced copies of various good and bad informative images with written texts mostly seen on the internet. Memes could also mean cultural composites (ideas, symbols, and behaviors) that circulated through replication and appropriation in various forms (Silvestri, 2014). Although it is usually based in popular culture, massively popularized, and shared via social media, blogs, email, and other avenues nowadays, it can also be thoughts, fragments of ideas, sounds, melodies, and various types of information (Amir, 2021). Some people nowadays develop and share more interactive memes on social media that cover a variety of topics. This can be used to convey a viewpoint on a societal norm, expose a social taboo, push a political agenda, reveal unspoken personal problems, inspire others to speak up, and, most significantly, to laugh about something (Amir, 2021). As the meme culture grows, it becomes evident that some memes' topic is expressed more on mental health concerns. Specific messages may impact people's attitudes, beliefs, and behaviors regarding mental health issues (Lebowitz and Ahn, 2014).

Depression, specifically, is a common and severe mental health condition that has a negative effect on how you feel, think, and behave (American Psychology Association, 2021), and it has been observed on a topic or subject of internet memes posted on social media. These internet memes related to depression has potential to improve the mood of depressed people in terms of humor, relatability and shareability. (Akram, et. al, 2020). In addition, memes related to mental illness are utilized to disguise symptoms and serve as a defense mechanism for individuals who have experienced depression or anxiety. (Kariko and Anasih, 2019). Because it is difficult to engage with others face-to-face, depressed or anxious people use social media to ease the symptoms (Andreassen et al., 2016). As a result, memes are used in a variety of ways to send a message about depression that does not always correspond to a consistent meaning (Chateau, 2020). With that, the internet memes can influence the perception and interpretation of public viewers about the online messages in a variety of context-of which oftentimes, internet memes are generally perceived as more likable yet less pressing in conveying messages (Hecker, 2020).

The strength of one's attitude influences one's actions significantly. Simply saying, the more powerful ones' attitude is, the more probable it is to impact a person's actions (McLeod, 2018). In this context, the researchers postulate that other people's attitudes conveyed on a meme about depression can impact viewers' perceptions of depressed people. Thus, the aim of this study is to determine the perceived attitudes of Facebook users towards memes about depression. Once determined, provision and strengthening of public awareness is needed in order to understand the interaction on digital replication of expressive memes about depression, as well as its impact on viewers' perceptions of depressed individuals.

Conceptual Framework

This study adopts the ABC (Affect, Behavioral, Cognitive) model of attitude. Accordingly, an individual's feelings towards an attitude item are referred to as *affective*, and the response of a person towards an attitude object is referred to as *behavior*, while the term *cognitive* refers to an individual's beliefs/perception about an attitude entity (Jain, 2014).

The box contained the profile of the participants, which asked about their sex and age. *Age* refers to the number of years people have lived, and only between 18-34 years old is applicable in this study. According to statistics, Filipinos aged between 18-34 year old were the largest group of Facebook users in the Philippines, (NapoleonCat, 2020; Statista, 2021). *Sex* refers to their biological sex of being male or female. Many researchers have argued that sociodemographic factors influence the response to and the identification, distribution, and assessment of mental illness (Corrigan & Watson, 2007; Von dem Knesebeck, Angermeyer, et al., 2013; Park, Kim, Cho, & Lee, 2015). Thus, these factors help shape the individual's beliefs and attitudes.

The role of each component on ABC Model of attitude thus determines the association between the participants' frequency of engagement with memes that convey depression and their attitude toward depression. *Affective* refers to a person's feelings and ideas about something depending on their attitude (McLeod, 2018). In this study, the affective context delves into the expressive illustration of memes about depression. These memes are provided as examples in this study's research questionnaire to help the participants internalize their feelings and thoughts on a receptive expression of memes about depression. Meanwhile, behavioural and cognitive contexts are being determined through the personal and perceived attitude towards depression, as well as the participants' and their frequency of interaction with memes that express depression. The *behavioural* component of this study relates to the participants' intents, or their reactions (whether they regard depression memes as comical or serious) after being exposed to it. Thus, it is important to regard that one's attitude has an impact on how a person will act or behave (McLeod, 2018).

On other hand, an individual's attitude towards an item cannot be established merely by identifying the ideas because emotion and the cognitive process regarding an attitude object operate together (Jain, 2014). The cognitive aspect holds an appraisal of the substance that serves as the foundation for a person's personal and perceived attitude toward depression (Jain, 2014). External influences have an impact on one's attitudes and beliefs, but they also can influence internal effects. Attitudes and ideas, like actions, are impacted by external events, but they may also be influenced purposefully by one's free will (McLeod, 2018).

Figure 1. Schematic Diagram of the Study

METHOD

This study is a quantitative research using a descriptive-correlational design. To describe relationships between variables and demographics, researchers utilized a descriptive correlational research design (Al-Ghabeesh & Mahmoud, 2021). Quantitative research techniques entail quantifying and analyzing variables in order to acquire results. It comprises the use of certain statistical methodologies to the analysis of numerical data in order to answer questions. Descriptive-correlational design is also utilized to describe the relationship between variables (Apuke, 2017). Moreover, it helps determine the relationship between perceived attitudes and memes expressing depression.

Participants

The study considered asking participants' personal and perceived attitude toward depression and their frequency participants' interaction with memes expressing depression. The researchers took several considerations in recruiting participants for this research

study. According to the Philippine Statistics Authority (2020), the total population of Surigao del Norte is 534,686, which the researchers used to calculate the sample size of 385 participants using Cochran's sample size calculation for a limited population. Moreover, participants should only have a single account on Facebook that they are actively using. Simple random sampling was used to select the participants. Each person of the population has an equal probability of getting chosen as a participant in this approach. When deriving conclusions from the findings of a study, an unbiased random sample and a representative sample are essential. Because of the representativeness of a sample acquired by simple random sampling, it is acceptable to generalize the sample's conclusions back to the population (Sharma, 2017)

Research Instrument

The researchers use a survey questionnaire and informed consent that are easy to read and include clear instructions written with simple English. The questionnaire consists of a standardized test—*Depression Stigma Scale (DSS)* by Kathleen Griffiths, Ph.D., and questions made by the researchers. It is divided into three sections. The **Part 1**. allows for a better understanding of the participants' profiles, particularly age and sex. The researchers create the second section of the survey questionnaire, and it consists of 3 sub-parts.

Part 2.1 Meme Selection Criteria

A summary of the key meme selection criteria, organized by stages of memes replication and general selection criteria for memes.

Stages/Selectors	Objective	Subjective	Inter-subjective	Meme-centered
Assimilation	distinctiveness	novelty	authority	self-justification
		simplicity	formality	
		coherence		
Retention	invariance	coherence	conformity	self-reinforcement
	controllability	utility		intolerance
Expression			expressivity	proselytism
Transmission			publicity	proselytism

Note. Adapted from *What makes a meme successful? Selection criteria for cultural evolution* Book, by Heylighen, F. (1998).

Mostly, the host disseminate internet memes in expressive context (Blackmore, 2000; Miller, 2017). Internet memes are popular in form of texts and image which is usually interpreted in a variety of ways by readers (Sanchez, 2020). It is necessary on comprehending online memes that requires a focus on human agency on understanding the information to be most likely influential to others (Shifman 2013a; Miltner, 2017). Thus, **researchers focused the criteria on assimilation stage identify the theme, self-loathing and worthlessness that is emphasized to any stages criteria such objective, subjective, inter subjective and meme-centered.**

In **assimilation stage**, the **object criteria** denote **distinctiveness** in terms of details or contrasting facts are more likely to be recognized and understood that the memes is about depression when it presents a context of worthlessness and self-loathing as one of the classifications in DSM-5. In **subjective criteria**, the memes about depression is a form of **novelty**, it is when the person who assimilates the meme about depression can make viewers' perceived a context of worthlessness and self-loathing. In the **inter-subject criteria**, the memes about depression propagate with one another based on **formality**, the host is at least express the original memetic substances of memes about depression to encourage the viewers to interact on the topic. In the **meme-centered criteria**, the **self-justification** is when viewers will understand and accept the host thoughts of worthlessness and self-loathing presented on a meme. Internet memes work because of their 'emotional resonance', accordingly internet memes enact mimetic gains a response for being humorous (Piata, 2018), but some depressed people use social media to ease the symptoms and being depressed is not funny (suicide is not), so it should not be mocked (Chateau, 2020: Andreassen et al., 2016).

The images below are examples of a memes that has a theme of self-loathing and worthlessness as defined on DSM-5 about depression. Also, the researchers decided to show the 4 memes based on using keywords such as 'depression meme' 'humorous depression meme', 'serious depression meme' when searching. The four pictures were also based on underlying factors such as their predisposition to convey valence and arousal, as well as the presence of affective content relevant to the experience of depression (e.g., death, suicide, isolation, hopelessness, depressed mood, manic symptoms), as outlined in the DSM-5 criteria for Major Depressive Disorder (Regier, D., Kuhl, E., and Kupfer D., 2013). This criteria in choosing is in accordance to what Akram, et. al (2020) did for their study "Exploratory study on the role of emotion regulation in perceived valence, humour, and beneficial use of depressive internet memes in depression".

Image 1. Serious Memes About self-loathing on assimilation stage.

The context of Memes posted by S.J. Foster is kind of self-loathing saying "I'm always depressed" and "Me making fun of my own suffering so it doesn't look that serious", a genuine message is detailed about depression that make a memes distinct in assimilation stage. In terms of subjective and inter subject criteria, a person named E. Martinez commented/participated "I feel ya brother", it means the public views understand what the

message convey. Thus, meme-centered criteria is successfully meet the assimilation stage to make it clear for viewers of what the memes meant for.

Image 2. Humorous about self-loathing on assimilation stage.

The context of memes posted on depression memes page is about self-loathing saying “When I’m deep in a depressive episode and someone tells me to ‘stay positive’.”, a mimic message tell about the personal experience on depression that make a memes distinct in assimilation stage. In terms of subjective and inter subjective criteria, many people participated on the comment section and consider the meme as relatable. Participants have mixed reaction response based on emoticons used such as laughing, loved, like, care, angry and sad. Thus, focusing on meme-centered criteria it successfully achieved the viewer’s understand the meaning of meme.

Image 3. Serious Memes About self-loathing on assimilation stage.

The context of memes posted by Hero Kun saying “Trust me, depression is not a joke”, a genuine message about depression that shared topic that maybe based on personal experience that makes a memes belong with the other depression memes. In terms of subjective and inter subject, the viewer’s perhaps watched the meme but nobody

participated. Thus, the meme-centered criteria was achieved because of viewers and its content about depression.

Image 4. Humorous memes about worthlessness in assimilation stage.

The context of memes posted on Ludicrous.glow is about depression, the person who shared the meme emphasized that “depression is not an excuse! It’s serious”. It is mimic because the meme tells that people used depression as excuse that somehow discard having mental illness. In terms of subjective and inter subject, the viewer’s perhaps watched the meme but nobody participated. Thus, the meme-centered criteria was achieved because of viewers and its content about depression.

Finally, the **Part 3** is based on a standardized test: *Depression Stigma Scale (DSS)* by Kathleen Griffiths, Ph.D., an 18 item 5-point Likert scale. The researchers decided to use the following questions from the standardized test: Under Personal Stigma Subscale – “People with depression could snap out of it if they wanted.”, “Depression is a sign of personal weakness.”, “Depression is not a real medical illness.”, “People with depression are dangerous.”, “It is best to avoid people with depression so that you don’t become depressed yourself.”, “People with depression are unpredictable.”, “If I had depression, I would not tell anyone.”, “I would not employ someone if I knew they had been depressed.”, and “I would not vote for a politician if I knew they had been depressed.”; Under Perceived Stigma Subscale – “Most people believe that people with depression could snap out of it if they wanted.”, “Most people believe that depression is a sign of personal weakness.”, “Most people believe that depression is not a real medical illness.”, “Most people believe that people with depression are dangerous.”, “Most people believe that it is best to avoid people with depression so that you don’t become depressed

yourself.”, “Most people believe that people with depression are unpredictable.”, “If they had depression, most people would not tell anyone.”, “Most people would not employ someone they knew had been depressed.” and “Most people would not vote for a politician they knew had been depressed.”.

According to Griffiths, *The Personal Stigma Subscale* assesses stigma in participants' attitude toward depression by asking them to rate their agreement with nine statements about depression. While *The Perceived Stigma Subscale* assesses a respondent's perception of others' attitudes about depression by asking them to indicate what they feel the majority of other people believe about nine statements. Each item is scored on a five-point Likert scale, one representing "strongly disagree" and five representing "strongly agree." Each subscale's total score varied from 0 to 36, with higher values indicating more significant stigma. The DSS has been shown to have sufficient internal consistency and test-retest reliability.

DSS Reliability result. According to Griffiths' norms and psychometric properties, Test-retest reliability is $r = 0.71$ ($n=435$) (DSS- Personal Stigma Subscale) and $r = 0.67$ ($n =434$) (DSS- Perceived Stigma Subscale). With a sample of 487, Internal consistency is $\alpha = 0.75$ (DSS- Personal Stigma Subscale), $\alpha = 0.75$ (DSS- Perceived Stigma Subscale), and $\alpha = 0.78$ (Total Depression Stigma Scale).

Pilot Test. The data gathered to 15 samples following three ethical principles and guidelines according to Belmont Report: *Principle of beneficence, principle of human dignity and the principle of justice*

Instrument		α	Remark
Part 2	How frequently do you laugh to memes about depression?	8.67	Highly reliable
	How frequently do you take serious of memes about depression?	8.93	Highly reliable
	How frequently do you interact with memes about depression generally?	9.12	Highly reliable
Part 3.1	Personal (9 indicators)	8.97	Highly reliable
Part 3.2	Perceived (9 indicators)	8.74	Highly reliable

Figure 3. *PILOT TEST RESULT*

Construct	Indicators	Scale Mean if Item Deleted	Scale Variance if Item Deleted	Corrected Item-Total Correlation	Cronbach's Alpha (α) if Item Deleted	Remark (Measure)
Personal	B1	20.1333	12.267	0.183	0.644	Good
	B2	20.4667	11.124	0.453	0.583	Good
	B3	21.3333	11.667	0.164	0.663	Good
	B4	20.5333	9.552	0.59	0.533	Good
	B5	21.5333	10.981	0.537	0.568	Good
	B6	20.5333	12.267	0.328	0.615	Good
	B7	21.6667	14.095	- 0.123	0.703	Good

	B8	20.6667	10.81	0.505	0.57	Good
	B9	20.8667	11.124	0.393	0.595	Good
Perceived	C1	22.2667	11.067	0.215	0.68	Good
	C2	22.2667	9.352	0.58	0.577	Good
	C3	22.6	12.971	- 0.044	0.731	Good
	C4	22.2	10.457	0.465	0.613	Good
	C5	22.9333	10.781	0.382	0.632	Good
	C6	22.4667	11.552	0.427	0.631	Good
	C7	22.3333	12.238	0.327	0.65	Good
	C8	22.3333	10.552	0.535	0.602	Good
	C9	22.3333	10.981	0.433	0.623	Good

Figure 4. *INTER-ITEM STATISTICS*

Data Analysis

Mean and Standard Deviation. Mean refers to the average scores collected from the raw data. The standard deviation is a statistic that calculates the square root of the variance and measures the dispersion of a dataset relatively to its mean. These statistical tools describe the average and spread of data on the following statement of the problems: *What is the participants' frequency of interaction with memes that express depression context (Humorous and Serious)?, What is the participants' frequency of interaction with memes that express depression in general?, and What is the participants' attitude towards depression (Personal and Perceived)?.*

Pearson Correlation. The test statistic Pearson's correlation coefficient assesses the statistical relationship, or association, between two continuous variables. It provides information on the magnitude and direction of the relationship's association, or correlation. This statistical tool measures the first null hypothesis regarding the significant relationship between the participants' attitude towards depression and their frequency of interaction with memes that express depression.

One-way ANOVA. In testing the second null hypothesis regarding the significant difference between the participants' attitude towards depression and their frequency of interaction with memes that express depression when grouped according to their profile variable, a One-way Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) was conducted. This was used to analyze if significant differences exist between the respective mean scores of groups. A 95% confidence interval was set. After which, the first step was to determine if the ANOVA result has a significant F test, in this case, any value lesser than ($\alpha=0.05$) is deemed statistically significant.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

This chapter explains the study's data analysis and findings. The following data can be found: a demographic profile (both sexes and ages); frequency of interaction in memes that both express humorous and serious depression, as well as general interaction on depression memes; personal and perceived attitudes toward depression. Moreover, it discusses the relationship and difference of the null hypotheses of the study: *Is there a significant relationship between the participants' attitude towards depression and their frequency of interaction with memes that express depression?* and *When grouped according to their profile variable, is there a significant difference between the participants' attitude towards depression and their frequency of interaction with memes that express depression?*.

Demographic Profile

Table 1. *Profile of the Respondents*

Profile Variables	f (n=385)	%
Sex		
Male	169	43.90
Female	216	56.10
Age		
15-19 years old	58	15.06
20-24 years old	217	56.36
25-29 years old	104	27.01
30-34 years old	6	1.56

One of the most core characteristics in determining the profile of the participants is their sex and age. In terms of sex, the majority of the participants were female, totalling in 216 (56.10 %), while 169 (43.90 %) were men out of 385 participants. This is in line with the aggregate statistics data from August 2021, which showed that the Philippines had 93 million Facebook users, the majority of whom were women (54%) (NapoleonCat, 2020; Statista, 2021).

Furthermore with a total population of 385, results showed that participants belong to ages 15-19 years old were 58 (15.06%), then 20-24 years old with 217 (56.36%), 25-29 years old with 104 (27.01%), and 30-34 years old with 6 (1.56%). In the Philippines, 31% of Facebook users are between the ages of 18 and 24 followed by 29% between the ages of 25-34 as of August 2021 which is in line with the results of the study (Statista, 2021).

Participants' frequency of interaction with memes that express depression.

Table 2. *frequency of interaction with memes that express depression.*

Indicators	\bar{X}	σ	Interpretation
How frequently do you laugh to memes about depression?	2.24	0.95	Rarely
How frequently do you seriously look at memes about depression?	2.77	0.78	Oftentimes
How frequently do you interact with memes about depression generally?	2.51	0.78	Oftentimes
Average	2.51	0.83	Oftentimes

Legend:

Scale	Range	Interpretation
4	3.25-4.00	All the time
3	2.50-3.24	Oftentimes
2	1.75-2.49	Rarely
1	1.00-1.74	Not at all

Results in table 2 shows that majority of the participants answered oftentimes on how they frequently interact with memes about depression in general ($\bar{X}=2.51, \sigma =0.78$). Memes have a significant impact on young people although the emerging visual culture may alter their perceptions of visual representation through digital media (Han, 2020). Viewers may perceive a variety of interpretations from a hilarious meme and the more popular the content becomes, the more interpretations there are; yet, interpretations are contingent on a culture's ability to be more open-minded (Laineste & Voolaid, 2016). Although, it is also worth mentioning that the participants in this study oftentimes prefer interacting on memes expressing depression seriously ($\bar{X}=2.77, \sigma =0.78$) rather than humorously ($\bar{X}=2.24, \sigma =0.95$).

Participants' attitude towards depression in terms of personal and perceived.

Table 3 participants' attitude towards depression in term if personal and perceived.

Indicators	\bar{X}	σ	Interpretation
Personal			
People with depression could snap out of it if they wanted.	2.76	0.86	Agree
Depression is a sign of personal weakness	2.14	0.89	Disagree
Depression is not a real medical illness	1.66	0.71	Strongly disagree
People with depression are dangerous.	2.59	0.92	Agree
It is best to avoid people with depression so that you don't become depressed yourself.	2.01	0.87	Disagree
People with depression are unpredictable.	3.06	0.68	Agree
If I had depression I would not tell anyone.	2.26	0.84	Disagree
I would not employ someone if I knew they had been depressed.	2.19	0.79	Disagree
I would not vote for a politician if I knew they had been depressed.	2.75	0.87	Agree
Average	2.38	0.83	Disagree
Perceived			
Most people believe that people with depression could snap out of it if they wanted.	3.01	0.66	Agree
Most people believe that depression is a sign of personal weakness.	2.56	0.89	Agree

Most people believe that depression is not a real medical illness.	2.25	0.87	Disagree
Most people believe that people with depression are dangerous.	2.83	0.75	Agree
Most people believe that it is best to avoid people with depression so that you don't become depressed yourself.	2.42	0.84	Disagree
Most people believe that people with depression are unpredictable.	3.07	0.55	Agree
If they had depression, most people would not tell anyone.	2.76	0.81	Agree
Most people would not employ someone they knew had been depressed.	2.53	0.76	Agree
Most people would not vote for a politician they knew had been depressed.	2.95	0.74	Agree
Average	2.71	0.76	Agree

Legend:

Scale	Range	Interpretation
4	3.25-4.00	Strongly Agree (SA)
3	2.50-3.24	Agree (A)
2	1.75-2.49	Disagree (D)
1	1.00-1.74	Strongly Disagree (SD)

Meanwhile table 3 presents the participants' attitude towards depression in terms of personal and perceived. The majority of participants disagreed ($\bar{X}=2.38$, $\sigma =0.83$) with the idea of having a personal negative attitude toward depressed people. While, majority of the participants agreed that most people around them (perceived) would have a negative attitude towards depressed people ($\bar{X}=2.71$, $\sigma =0.76$). These findings are consistent with prior research, which found that perceived stigma was consistently higher than personal stigma in the general population (Reavley & Jorm, 2011); Coppens, 2013; Yang et al., 2020).

Moreover, mental illnesses are widely ignored or feared by Asians, according to a prior research (Ng, 1997; Yang et al., 2020). This notion can be supported in statements *People with depression could snap out of it if they wanted* ($\bar{X}=2.76$, $\sigma =0.86$), *People with depression are dangerous* ($\bar{X}=2.38$, $\sigma =0.83$), *People with depression are unpredictable* ($\bar{X}=3.06$, $\sigma =0.68$), and *I would not vote for a politician if I knew they had been depressed* ($\bar{X}=2.75$, $\sigma =0.87$) which most participants agreed on the said statements. On the other hand, most participants agreed that most people around them would believe the following statements *Most people believe that people with depression could snap out of it if they wanted* ($\bar{X}=3.01$, $\sigma =0.66$), *Most people believe that depression is a sign of personal weakness* ($\bar{X}=2.56$, $\sigma =0.89$), *Most people believe that people with depression are dangerous* ($\bar{X}=2.83$, $\sigma =0.75$), *Most people believe that people with depression are unpredictable* ($\bar{X}=3.07$, $\sigma =0.55$), *If they had depression, most people would not tell anyone* ($\bar{X}=2.76$, $\sigma =0.81$), *Most people would not employ someone they knew had been depressed* ($\bar{X}=2.53$, $\sigma =0.76$), and *Most people would not vote for a politician they knew had been depressed* ($\bar{X}=2.95$, $\sigma =0.74$). Although negative perception in mental health is still a worldwide issue, there is evidence that the sociocultural context (collective and individual values, aspirations, norms, and social expectations) can influence how negative perception

is exhibited and the intensity of reputation in various social groups (Yang et al., 2007, 2013; Lien et al., 2015; Chang et al., 2016; Mascayano et al., 2020). One thing to emphasize also is that most of the participants strongly disagree on the statement *Depression is not a real medical illness* which can be supported by a 2018 survey that resulted with 78% participants believing that depression is considered a mental illness (APA, 2019).

Significant relationship between the participants’ attitude towards depression and their frequency of interaction with memes that express depression.

Table 4. The significant relationship between the participants’ attitude towards depression and their frequency of interaction with memes that express depression

Interaction	Attitude	p-value	Decision
Frequency of interaction	Personal	0.0086	Reject H ₀
	Perceived	0.0143	Reject H ₀

As presented in the table, there is a significant relationship between the participants’ attitude towards depression and their frequency of interaction with memes that express depression. The study’s findings resulted in rejecting the null hypothesis between the participants’ attitude (both personal and perceived) towards depression and their frequency of interaction with memes that express depression. The computed p-values between personal attitude and memes expressing depression ($p = 0.0086$) and perceived attitude and memes expressing depression ($p = 0.0143$) are both less than the 0.05 significance level. This supports with how internet memes can influence public viewers' perception and understanding of internet activities in a number of contexts (Hecker, 2020).

Significant difference between the participants’ attitude towards depression and their frequency of interaction with memes that express depression.

Table 5. The significant difference between the participants’ attitude towards depression and their frequency of interaction with memes that express depression.

Profile Variables	Dependent Variables	p-value	Decision
Sex	Interaction	0.2466	Do not reject H ₀
	Personal	0.4054	Do not reject H ₀
	Perceived	0.0259	Reject H ₀
Age	Interaction	0.0129	Reject H ₀
	Personal	0.0000	Reject H ₀
	Perceived	0.0283	Reject H ₀

The results, as shown in the table, revealed a variety of outcomes. A one-way ANOVA revealed that there was a significant difference in *perceived attitude towards depression* between sexes ($p = 0.0259 < \alpha = 0.05$). This finding is supported by one study from Chile and Colombia which there was a significant difference on gender in the DSS-Personal scores, with women scoring lower than males (Martinez et al., 2020). However, there's no significant difference between sexes and the following problems: *personal attitude towards depression* ($p = 0.4054 > \alpha = 0.05$) and *frequency of interaction with memes that express depression* ($p = 0.2466 > \alpha = 0.05$). These findings are consistent with one study's findings that found no gender differences on the DSS-Personal subscale in a sample of Arab teenagers (Dardas et al., 2017) and another study results that stated there was no significant difference in meme awareness based on an individual's sex (Laranjo, 2020).

On the other hand, a one-way ANOVA revealed that there was a significant difference when grouped by age between the following problems: *perceived attitude towards depression* ($F = 3.06, p = 0.0283 < \alpha = 0.05$), *personal attitude towards depression* ($F = 11.33, p = 0.0000 < \alpha = 0.05$), and *frequency of interaction with memes that express depression* ($F = 3.64, p = 0.0129 < \alpha = 0.05$). According to prior studies, there may be generational differences in mental health knowledge because younger participants may have a better level of mental health awareness and hence support less negative perceptions about depression than middle-aged or elderly individuals (Griffiths & Jorm, 2008; Reavley et al., 2014; Yang et al., 2020).

Findings

The findings of the study are revealed as follows:

1. In terms of the profile demographics, 56% of the 385 participants are female, while 44% are male. As per the results, the majority of those who responded to the study survey are females. In terms of age, 385 participants are 56% of the age 20-24 years old, followed by 27% of the age 25-29 years, then 15% of the age 15-19 years old, and lastly 1.56% of the age 30-34 years old. Majority of the participants' ages were 20-24 years old.
2. The participants rarely interact with memes that express depression through humorous context ($\bar{X} = 2.24, \sigma = 0.95$). While, the participants oftentimes interact with memes that express depression through serious context ($\bar{X} = 2.77, \sigma = 0.78$). In general, majority of the participants oftentimes interact with memes expressing depression ($\bar{X} = 2.51, \sigma = 0.78$).
3. The majority of participants disagree ($\bar{X} = 2.38, \sigma = 0.83$) with the idea of having a personal negative attitude toward depressed people. While, majority of the participants agree that the most people around them (perceived) would have a negative attitude towards depressed people ($\bar{X} = 2.71, \sigma = 0.76$).
4. The study's findings resulted in rejecting the null hypothesis between the participants' attitudes both personal ($p = 0.0086 < \alpha = 0.05$) and perceived ($p = 0.0143 < \alpha = 0.05$) towards depression and their frequency of interaction with memes that express

depression. This suggests that there is a significant relationship between the participants' attitude towards depression and their frequency of interaction with memes that express depression.

5. When being grouped by sex, a one-way ANOVA revealed that there was a statistically significant difference in perceived attitude towards depression ($p = 0.0259 < \alpha = 0.05$) which would reject the null hypothesis. Although, there's no significant difference in the following problems: personal attitude towards depression ($p = 0.4054 > \alpha = 0.05$) and frequency of interaction with memes that express depression ($p = 0.2466 > \alpha = 0.05$) between sexes. The two latter results in not rejecting the null hypothesis.
6. When being grouped by age, a one-way ANOVA revealed that there was a significant difference between the following problems: perceived attitude towards depression ($p = 0.0283 < \alpha = 0.05$), personal attitude towards depression ($p = 0.0000 < \alpha = 0.05$), and frequency of interaction with memes that express depression ($p = 0.0129 < \alpha = 0.05$). Thus fully rejecting the null hypothesis that states there is no significant difference between the participants' attitude towards depression and their frequency of interaction with memes that express depression when grouped according to their profile: Age.

Conclusions

Based on the indicated findings, the following conclusions were drawn:

1. The majority of the Facebook users who participated are within the age of 20-24 years old and are primarily female.
2. When it comes to memes expressing depression, people would interact with it seriously rather than humorously. This suggests that specific values are involved when interacting with memes expressing depression.
3. Although the participants are personally aware of the concept of depression, the people around them do not. This implies that the general population of Surigao del Norte still has insufficient understanding of depression as a mental illness.
4. Facebook users' perceptions and understanding of depression and depressed people can be influenced by internet memes whether if it is humorous or serious.
5. In general, memes that express depression are interacted with both sexes at all ages. This supports the idea that memes are for everyone, regardless of their context.

Thus, it is important to remind Facebook users to tread carefully while engaging with memes.

Recommendations

The results of our study were indicated by the cumulative analysis of the questionnaire responses. As a result, the researchers made the following suggestions:

1. For Facebook users, the researchers want to emphasize that there's a wide range of content available on the internet. Whatever content they interact with should not directly imply a poor opinion about another person.
2. For Content Creators, there should be accountability when publishing materials (such as memes) that deal with themes such as depression while making content. Creating materials with topics like depression should be taken seriously and be based on facts.
3. For Psychology Clubs and other Organizations, hosting programs aimed at the general public regarding Depression as a mental illness can help improve its perception and bring more awareness about it.
4. For Guidance Counselors, assisting students in being more conscious of their attitudes and behaviors may help lessen negative perceptions about mental illness. This could be conducted by one-on-one counseling or holding a seminar/ workshop about the pros and cons of Facebook content such as memes expressing depression.
5. For future researchers who will utilize this work as a basis for their related studies, specific genders (such as transgender, non-binary, etc.) could be tested for significant relationships on levels of attitude towards depression.
6. More research must be done on the survey questionnaires (especially parts 1 and 2), and if possible, find a standardized test pertaining to memes that can be utilized.
7. In terms of sample size, it's better to keep it within the researchers' university first so that the findings may directly benefit the school.
8. It is also suggested that this study can be conducted as Qualitative Research.
9. Investigating factors such as religion and cultural differences influencing the attitude of participants regarding depression is encouraged.

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